

FEATURES OF CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS FOR B₁ LEVEL LEARNERS*M. Sultonova*¹*Abstract:*

Critical thinking is the process of considering ideas in many positions, in accordance with their meaningful connections, comparing them with other ideas. It is the result and the moment in thinking when the critical approach becomes natural through interaction with ideas and information, it is an active process, or stimulated, or happens spontaneously and provides the student with the opportunity to control the information, question it, combine, remake, adapt or reject. The article deals with the issues based on the theory of critical thinking and ways of its developing.

Key words: critical thinking, tasks, thinking, information, control.

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At present, the most important tasks of the modern school are the maximum disclosure of the individual abilities of each student, the education of a whole personality, ready for life in a high-tech, rapidly changing world. Modern society, like modern education, needs a free, creatively developed personality, endowed with certain qualities of thinking. Freedom of thinking determines its critical orientation, focused on constructive and creative activity, therefore critical thinking is a qualitative characteristic of a free person. Our time is a time of changes and transformations in various spheres of life. Entering a new era, humanity is in need of a radical modification and a change in orientation towards tolerance and democracy. The new 21st century confronts us not only with the fact of the emergence of a specific situation of POST (-modernism, -industrialism ...), but also requires constant self-formation, adaptation to changes, reassessment of values.

Therefore, right now, the “question of time” is critical thinking - thinking about changing thinking.

Reforming education, in our opinion, is an attempt to critically comprehend the current situation and determine the priorities of state policy in the development of education. This is where critical thinking can help. The active formation of society, the intensive processes of globalization and informatization require a completely new type of thinking from a modern applicant for education, which will allow him to adapt to constant social changes, generate new ideas, as well as carry out a comprehensive analysis of the information received and give it an objective assessment.

That is why critical thinking plays an important role in the modern educational space, which is the basis of educational activities. The organization of the educational process of any educational institution should be aimed primarily at the formation of critical thinking of students, which will help them master the basic competencies

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that are necessary for the socialization of the individual and the formation of his individuality.

Today, critical thinking is becoming the technological basis of modern education, its formation is dictated by various social shifts and the continuous reform of society.

It is worth noting that a person, trying to find the truth, turned to the foundations of criticism, which were started in ancient philosophy by Xenophon, Socrates, Plato and were actively introduced into the activities of ancient Greek schools. Since ancient times, a person has been interested in everything that surrounds him, he tried to understand who he is, what his vocation is. Undoubtedly, the search for answers to questions that arose in the process of mastering the environment stimulated the formation of analytical, critical thinking and logic. Sorina G.V. noted that "the criticality of thinking acts as a scientific and philosophical problem in the Enlightenment, as a means of introducing the ideas of forming a free and responsible individual in society" [7]. Voltaire, J.J. Rousseau, I. Kant, D. Hume and J. Locke believed that the formation and process of formation of a harmonious and creative citizen should be viewed precisely through the prism of criticism. It is also worth noting that the main postulates of the classical German philosophy of society are based on the phenomenon of criticism. As you can see, the critical thinking interested a person at all stages of its formation. That is why in the XX century. In the United States, the idea of forming critical thinking arose. It is widely represented in the works of famous American psychologists of the 20th century. W. James and J. Dewey. Also, the problems of the formation of critical thinking were studied by D. Kluster, D. Halpern, A. Crawford, M. Lipman, K. Meredith, S. Matthews, R. Sternberg, D. Steele, Ch. Temple and others.

Given the heterogeneity of views and approaches to the interpretation of critical thinking, modern pedagogy has a significant number of author's interpretations of this concept. In particular, the author of the monograph "The Psychology of Critical Thinking" D. Halpern points out that "critical thinking is the use of cognitive techniques or strategies that increase the likelihood of obtaining the desired end result. This type of thinking, which is used in solving problems, formulating conclusions, probable evaluation and decision making. Critical thinking is sometimes also called directed thinking..." [9, p. 20].

So, in pedagogy and methods of teaching subjects, the issue of the need to form the thinking of learners, their conscious perception of what they are learning, the ability to apply higher-level mental (mental) operations in the process of mastering the material was considered quite widely. At the same time, it should be noted that the problem of introducing the technology of forming critical thinking has not yet been the subject of special studies.

The implementation of the competency-based approach in education encourages the search for new ideas, technologies that would contribute to the development and self-realization of the student's personality, to consciously and critically master reality, to possess a system of key and subject competencies. There are quite a lot of such technologies, and one of such promising pedagogical technologies is the technology of forming the critical thinking of learners.

G. Lindsay noted that independence of judgments is one of the signs of critical thinking, he emphasized that such thinking is aimed at creative mental activity, and not at reproduction based on rigid algorithms and stereotypes. A creative approach is mandatory in situations of comparing annual judgments and identifying alternatives based on taking into account the priorities of factors that determine the truth and reliability of information in general and the judgments made in particular [2].

According to G. Paul, a leading American specialist in the field of theory and practice of teaching critical thinking, critical thinking is organized, rational, directed thinking that skillfully pursues the goal of thinking in a certain area of knowledge or human interests. This is thinking about thinking, when a person thinks in order to improve his thinking [6].

A. Crawford expressed his position, according to which critical thinking is rational reflective thinking, which determines what to believe and question [5].

The modern researcher A. Tyaglo explains critical thinking as an activity of the mind aimed at identifying and correcting one's mistakes, the accuracy of statements and the validity of reasoning. He argues that critical thinking follows from the awareness of the inevitability of error and error in human cognition. It is a specific type of reflexes based on the knowledge of elementary logic and relevant specific sciences [4]. Researchers V. Makarenko and A. Tumantsova believe that critical thinking lies in the ability of an individual to strictly evaluate his thoughts and extraneous influences, identify strengths and weaknesses in them, not to consider every guess as true, but to question and verify it [3].

In fact, a person who thinks critically has no boundaries, no barriers to his own formation. His intellectual formation not only does not stop after graduating from school, university, but also intensifies, because new expanses of raw information appear. Such a person is tolerant, he is aware that the problem can have several solutions, each of which must be analyzed and evaluated.

Another feature is the ability to recognize the correctness of the positions of others, even if this contradicts one's own convictions. In addition, you need to pay attention to the fact that one of the main features of a person who thinks critically is the importance of developing and improving himself, and not emphasizing his own achievements. He also tries to avoid the temptation to use his own intellectual achievements to influence someone in a dishonest way. The process of obtaining new information, its analysis, research, and not the consumption of already explained material is very important. An analysis of scientific literature allows us to highlight the main characteristics of a person who thinks critically:

Independence. Thinking can be critical only when it is individual. No one can think critically instead of us, so we need to create our own model of behavior, use certain methods to process the information received and have our own view on a particular problem.

Curiosity. A person who thinks critically is interested in everything that surrounds him. The formation of his critical thinking begins with the formulation of questions and clarification of the problems that need to be solved.

The presence of a convincing argument. Critical thinking involves finding your own solution to a problem and backing it up with sound evidence.

Sociality. Our own opinion is polished daily by society. When we read, argue with others, exchange opinions, we clarify, strengthen and strengthen our position.

Persistence. To obtain certain information or form our own position, we have to process a significant amount of material.

So, a person who thinks critically is a person who has developed not only the ability to analyze, synthesize, generalize information, defend his position, arguing it, but also stable moral qualities prevail, which allow in a modern informative society to draw a clear multi-colored picture of the world, where the ability to take responsibility, tolerantly cooperate with others in society, and have clear value orientations is important. For a person to be critically thinking, he/she needs certain knowledge and skills, as well as personal qualities and readiness for critical behavior. We reveal all this in the components of the structure of the formation of critical thinking. The cognitive component characterizes the cognitive abilities of learners, such as the perception of educational material, knowledge of the subject, knowledge of critical thinking. The use of this cognitive knowledge increases the likelihood of obtaining the desired result, that is, the developed critical thinking of learners. The analytical component includes such forms of thinking as consistency, reflection, checking the accuracy of statements. Let's consider them in more detail.

Logic is the formation of the sequence of the thought process, the rigor of the proof, the ability to draw generalizing conclusions. Consistency is necessary for the formation of critical thinking, since information must be analyzed from the standpoint of logic. Reflection is the process of self-knowledge by the subject of internal mental acts and states [8]. Reflection is usually considered in connection with a person's ability to self-development and with this process itself.

Students should be able to apply what they have learned to both standard and non-standard situations.

Verification of the accuracy of statements (assessment) - establishes the absolute or comparative value of any object or problem. Without evaluation, critical thinking is impossible. Many researchers call critical thinking evaluative and include evaluation as one of the main features of critical thinking.

The personal component reveals the qualities of a person capable of critical thinking. Today we can talk about the exhaustion of the classical pedagogical paradigm, according to which the personality was determined to a greater extent by the structure and nature of its objective activity, and the formation of the personality was carried out according to the given properties [8]. The student's personality resources are considered as a set of his potential opportunities for self-realization in activity [6]. A learner, mediating by his activity the diverse and numerous influences of social institutions of education, is a true subject, because, being open to pedagogical influences, he perceives them selectively through internal attitudes, beliefs, values that can be successfully formed within the framework of a personality-developing complex [7]. Level of English B₁ or Pre-Intermediate - the average degree of English proficiency according to the common European scale of language competence CEFR. At this stage, you can understand English, correspond and communicate in everyday situations, travel, work and study, including with native speakers.

Critical thinking while learning foreign language helps to acquire such skills: analyze information, evaluate its reliability, evaluate your thoughts and extraneous influences on them, identify strengths and weaknesses in them, carefully consider

different approaches to a problem in order to make informed decisions on it; formulate independent judgments and build convincing arguments; to reflect and correct their own activities.

To form cognitive motives, in learners with B1 level it is necessary to apply both methods of stimulating interest in learning (cognitive games, educational discussions, emotional and moral situations and organizational and activity games), as well as methods of stimulating responsibility and duty (belief in the importance of learning, encouragement and punishment, making demands). As well as, it is important to develop individual project activity, which is carried out under the guidance of teachers.

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